

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

ВИВЧЕННЯ ВІТЧИЗНЯНОГО РИНКУ ЛІКАРСЬКИХ ЗАСОБІВ ДЛЯ ЛІКУВАННЯ ГАСТРИТУ

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STUDY OF THE DOMESTIC PHARMACEUTICAL MARKET FOR GASTRITIS TREATMENT

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АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті проаналізовано асортимент лікарських засобів для лікування гастриту на вітчизняному фармацевтичному ринку України. Його вивчили за Державним реєстром лікарських засобів України, довідником лікарських засобів Компендіум онлайн, Анатомо-терапевтично-хімічною класифікацією, інтернет-ресурсами з пошуку лікарських засобів в аптеках України – Apteki.ua і Tabletki.ua.

За даними Державного реєстру лікарських засобів України, станом на кінець 2023 року в Україні наявні 174 торгові назви лікарських засобів для лікування гастриту. Аналіз асортименту лікарських засобів показав, що на фармацевтичному ринку України переважають лікарські засоби закордонного виробництва (59 %). Серед країн-імпортерів лікарських засобів першість за номенклатурою лікарських засобів належить Індії (30 %). Лідером серед вітчизняних фірм-виробників є ТзОВ «Фармацевтична компанія «Здоров'я» (19 %). Частка однокомпонентних лікарських засобів для лікування гастриту на вітчизняному фармацевтичному ринку становить 83 %, комбінованих лікарських засобів – 9 %, двокомпонентних – 8 %.

Оскільки на вітчизняному фармацевтичному ринку України переважають лікарські засоби закордонного виробництва, що застосовують для лікування гастриту, результати аналізу асортименту підтверджують актуальність розробки нового вітчизняного лікарського засобу, який можна було б використовувати в терапії пацієнтів із цим захворюванням.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the assortment of medicines for the treatment of gastritis on the domestic pharmaceutical market of Ukraine. The assortment of medicines was studied using the State Register of Medicines of Ukraine, the Compendium of Medicines Compendium Online, the Anatomical-Therapeutic-Chemical classification, and internet resources for searching medicines in Ukrainian pharmacies, Apteki.ua and Tabletki.ua.

According to the data from the State Register of Medicines of Ukraine, as of the end of 2023, there are 174 trade names of medicines available in Ukraine for the treatment of gastritis. These medicines are presented in 304 assortment positions. The analysis of the assortment of drugs showed that foreign-made medicines predominate in the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine (59%). Among the importing countries of medicines, India leads (30%).

The leader among domestic manufacturing firms is LLC "Pharmaceutical Company Zdorovya" (19%). The share of single-component medicines for the treatment of gastritis in the domestic pharmaceutical market is 83%, combined preparations - 9%, and two-component ones - 8%.

Since foreign-made medicines predominantly dominate the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine for the treatment of gastritis, the results of the assortment analysis confirm the relevance of developing new domestic medicines that could be used in the therapy of patients with this condition.

Ключові слова: лікарські засоби, аналіз фармацевтичного ринку, країни-виробники, лікарські форми.

Keywords: medicines, pharmaceutical market analysis, manufacturing countries, medicinal forms.

Diseases of the digestive organs often have a chronic nature with regular relapses and complications, which sometimes may require surgical intervention. The most common among these diseases are gastritis and duodenitis, cholecystitis, peptic ulcer of the duodenum, and others [1].

A significant argument emphasizing the medical and social significance of digestive organ diseases is their prevalence in all age groups of the population: among working-age individuals, the elderly, children, and adolescents [2].

Gastritis is an inflammation of the gastric mucosa, which is a widespread disease affecting millions of people worldwide. The prevalence of gastritis varies in different regions, often increasing with age and being associated with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection, considered the main etiological factor in the development of gastritis and other gastroduodenal diseases. WHO notes that a significant portion of the world's population is infected with *H. pylori*. The prevalence of this disease is higher in developing countries due to lower hygiene standards and problems with access to clean drinking water [3].

Additionally, the risk of developing this disease may be associated with poor quality of nutrition, its improper balance, insufficient organization of nutrition at home and at work, psychoemotional stress, self-medication, and seeking qualified medical assistance at a late stage.

From the perspective of therapeutic approaches, a significant portion of therapeutic prescriptions for pa-

tients with digestive organ diseases consists of remedies for treating acid-related disorders and medicines used for the treatment of functional gastrointestinal disorders. Therefore, the purpose of our work was to analyze the assortment of medicines for the treatment of gastritis on the domestic pharmaceutical market of Ukraine.

Materials and Methods: The object of the study was information about registered medicines in Ukraine, available on the website of the Normative Directive Documents of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine [1].

The assortment of medicines was examined using the State Register of Medicines of Ukraine, the Compendium of Medicines Compendium Online, the Anatomical-Therapeutic-Chemical classification, and internet resources for searching medicines in Ukrainian pharmacies, Apteki.ua and Tabletki.ua.

During the work, the following methods were used: marketing, mathematical-statistical, logical generalization, and graphical. The results were systematized and presented in diagrams with explanations and conclusions [4, 5].

Results and Discussion: In Ukraine, as of November 2023, 26 medicines were registered by INN, which are represented by 174 trade names for the treatment of gastritis. These medicines are presented in 304 assortment positions (AP).

On the Ukrainian pharmaceutical market, medicines for the treatment of gastritis are available as domestic (41%; 125 AP) and imported (59%; 179 AP) products.

Figure 1. Diagram of the ratio of domestic to imported medicines for the treatment of gastritis

Among domestic manufacturing companies, the leading positions in terms of the nomenclature of medicines are held by: LLC "Pharmaceutical Company Zdorovya" – 19%, PJSC "Pharmaceutical Company Darnytsia" – 10%, PJSC "Lubnypharm" – 9%, PJSC "Kyivmedpreparat" – 8%, JSC "Farmak" – 8%. The shares of others are smaller: JSC "Kyiv Vitamin Plant"

– 6%, LLC "Kusum Pharm" – 5%, PJSC "Liktravy" – 5%, PJSC Pharmaceutical Factory "Viola" – 4%, LLC "AstraPharm" – 3%, PJSC "Lekhim-Kharkiv" – 3%, PJSC "Halychpharm" – 2%, PJSC SIC "Borshchahivskiy CPP" – 2%, and others (together accounting for 16% of the assortment of medicines).

Figure 2.

Diagram of the ratio of domestic pharmaceutical companies producing medicines for the treatment of gastritis

Medicines for the treatment of gastritis are supplied to the Ukrainian market by manufacturing firms from 23 countries around the world. During the analysis of the State Register of Medicines, the share of each manufacturing country in the product assortment was determined. The leaders are medicines manufactured in

India (30%; 53 AP), Turkey (12%; 21 AP), Slovenia (7%; 13 AP), Italy (6%, 11 AP), Germany (5%, 10 AP), Spain (5%, 9 AP), and Hungary (5%, 10 AP). Other countries, whose import of medicines for the treatment of gastritis is smaller, collectively constitute 30% of the Ukrainian pharmaceutical market (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Diagram of the ratio of countries as producers by the number of registered medicines for the treatment of gastritis in the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine

Depending on the number of medicines, single-component, two-component, and multi-component medicines are distinguished. Among the registered medicines for the treatment of gastritis, single-compo-

nent products account for 83% (254 AP), two-component products comprise 8% (24 AP), while the share of combined medicines is minor, constituting 9% (26 AP) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Diagram of the distribution of medicines by composition

The analyzed medicines are represented on the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine in various pharmaceutical forms (Figure 5). The most common are products in tablet form, accounting for 56% (171 AP). Capsules rank second in terms of the number of offerings, constituting 11% (33 AP). The share of powders for preparing solutions for injections is 11% (38 AP). A slightly smaller share of medicines for the treatment of

gastritis is in the form of medicinal plant raw materials (6%, 17 AP), suspension (5%; 15 AP), and infusion solution (2%, 7 AP). The smallest share consists of drops, liquid extracts, gel, combined sets of tablets and capsules, oils, granules for preparing oral solutions, and granules for preparing suspensions for oral administration - each comprising 1%.

Figure 5. Diagram of the distribution of medicines by pharmaceutical form

Figure 6. Diagram of the depth of inventory of medicines for the treatment of gastritis

When analyzing the availability of medicines for treating gastritis in Ternopil pharmacies, one can compare the depth of product assortment in these pharmacies with the overall assortment of medicines in group A02B C. The greatest depth of stock was observed in the "Podorozhnyk/BAM/OSHAD" pharmacy chain, with a stock completeness of 86%, followed by

"Apteka nyzkykh tsin" pharmacy chains – 79%, "ANC" pharmacy chain – 78%, D.S. – 74%, "Dobrogo dnia/1 socialna/Iod" pharmacy chain – 71%, "Bazhayemo zdorovya" pharmacy chain – 70%, "Farmako" pharmacy chain – 58%, and "31" pharmacy chain – 52%. The depth of stock in 4 other pharmacy chains was less than 50% [6, 7].

Table 1

The structure of the assortment of medicines for the treatment of gastritis of group A02

No.	Groups of medicines according to the ATC classification
1	A02A B – Aluminum compounds
2	A02A D – Combinations and complexes of aluminum, calcium, and magnesium compounds
3	A02A F – <u>Antacids with antiflatulents</u>
4	A02B A – H ₂ -receptor antagonists
5	A02B B – Prostaglandins
6	A02B C – Proton pump inhibitors
7	A02B D – <u>Combinations for eradication of Helicobacter pylori</u>
8	A02B X – <u>Other drugs for peptic ulcer and gastro-oesophageal reflux disease (GORD/GERD)</u>

Among the selected medicines for treating gastritis, 8 groups were identified according to the ATC classification. These include: A02A B – Aluminum compounds, A02A D – Combinations and complexes of aluminum, calcium, and magnesium compounds, A02A F – Antacids in combination with drugs reducing intestinal gas formation, A02B A – H₂-receptor antagonists, A02B B – Prostaglandins, A02B C – Proton pump inhibitors, A02B D – Combinations for Helicobacter pylori eradication, A02B X – Other drugs for the treatment of peptic ulcer and gastroesophageal reflux disease.

According to the ATC classification, the analyzed medicines used for treating gastritis belong to the main

therapeutic group of drugs for treating acid-related disorders, as well as the following groups: A01A D – Other drugs for topical use in dentistry, A03 – Drugs used in case of functional gastrointestinal disorders, J – Systemic antimicrobial agents used for the treatment of gastritis, as of 2023 [8, 9].

Conclusions:

1. According to the State Register of Medicines of Ukraine, as of the end of 2023, there were 174 trade names available for treating gastritis in Ukraine.

2. Analysis of the assortment of medicines showed that foreign-made pharmaceuticals dominate the Ukrainian pharmaceutical market (59%). Among the importing countries of medicines, India (30%), Turkey

(12%), and Slovenia (7%) lead in terms of the nomenclature of medicines.

The leading domestic manufacturers among firms are LLC "Pharmaceutical Company "Zdorovya" (19%). The share of single-component medicines for treating gastritis on the domestic pharmaceutical market is 82%, two-component ones – 8%, and combination preparations – 9%. Since foreign-made pharmaceuticals predominantly dominate the Ukrainian pharmaceutical market for treating gastritis, the results of the assortment analysis confirm the relevance of developing and introducing a new domestic medicinal product that could be used in the therapy of patients with this condition.

Prospects for further research:

The results of the analysis indicate the feasibility of developing and introducing domestic medicines for the treatment of gastritis into the pharmaceutical market of Ukraine.

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